

MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION IN CLASSROOMS: COLLOQUIUM OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. This study explores the insights gained from a colloquium of secondary school teachers on multicultural education in classrooms. The colloquium provided a platform for teachers to engage in collaborative discussions and share their experiences, challenges, and effective practices related to implementing multicultural education. The target population for this study will be the twelve (12) participants from the line-up of public high school faculty, a junior high school unit who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. Through qualitative analysis of the colloquium proceedings, this study examines the key themes that emerged, including addressing challenges, addressing intersectionality, addressing diversity, educational equity, teacher preparation, enhancing learning outcomes, culturally responsive teaching, culturally responsive teaching, teacher professional development. The findings of the study disclosed the culturally responsive pedagogy, teacher professional development, and community engagement in fostering a culturally inclusive and equitable learning environment. The study contributes to the existing literature by providing insights from the perspectives of secondary school teachers, thus informing educators, policymakers, and researchers about the essential elements necessary for successful multicultural education implementation. The findings from this colloquium serve as a valuable resource for educational stakeholders aiming to enhance diversity, equity, and inclusion within the educational system.

KEY WORDS

1. Multicultural Education in Classrooms
2. Colloquium of Secondary School Teacher
3. Educational Stakeholders

1. Introduction

Multicultural education is important for addressing issues of discrimination, bias, and marginalization, but teachers must be equipped with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes to effectively implement it in their classrooms. However, the success of multicultural education in diverse classrooms depends largely on the perceptions and experiences of teachers. Teachers play a crucial role in creating a classroom culture that is inclusive, respectful, and responsive to the needs of diverse learners. They must be equipped with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to effectively implement multicultural education in their classrooms. In global context, Kind and sensitive to the requirements of a variety of students. Teachers must be given the tools they need to successfully apply multicultural education in their classrooms, including the information, abilities, and attitudes. This book explores the function of teacher education in preparing instructors for instruction in diverse classrooms. It is titled Teacher Education for

Diversity: Critical Perspectives. It presents critical viewpoints on the current teacher preparation programs and makes recommendations for creating more efficient programs that are also sensitive to cultural differences. (Gay, G., 2020). In national context, Multicultural education is an important issue in the Philippines due to the country's diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds. Several studies have been conducted to explore teachers' perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms (Haddad, Y., Maty, M. 2019). Supported with another study by Bonto (2017) examined the perceptions of teachers regarding multicultural education in Philippine classrooms. The study found that teachers had a positive perception of multicultural education and recognized its importance in promoting tol-

erance and understanding among students from different cultural backgrounds. However, some teachers expressed concerns about their lack of knowledge and training in implementing multicultural education. In the local context, one study by Mella and Lim (2018) examined the perceptions and experiences of teachers in implementing multicultural education in a Philippine university in Region IV-A. The study found that teachers had positive perceptions of multicultural education and recognized its importance in promoting diversity and inclusion in the classroom. However, teachers faced several challenges in implementing multicultural education, including a lack of support from the school administration and limited resources for teaching materials.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this study is to examine the teachers' opinions and experiences with integrating intercultural education in different classrooms is the goal of this qualitative research study. This study specifically intends to investigate the difficulties, opportunities, and methods that teachers employ to promote multicultural education in their classes. This study aims to add to the body of information on multicultural education in education by gaining an understanding of teachers' viewpoints to help design successful techniques for promoting multicultural education in diverse classrooms.

1.2. Research Questions—Specifically, this study sought to answer on the following questions:

- (1) What is the lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms?
- (2) How do teachers' cope with challenges of multi-cultural education?
- (3) What educational management insight can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—To make the study more comprehensive to the readers and beneficiaries the following terms will be defined based on the objectives or purpose of the study entitled multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. Multicultural education in classrooms refers to an approach to teaching and learning that recognizes and values the diversity of students' cultural backgrounds, experiences, and identities. It aims to create an inclusive and equitable learning environment where all students, regardless

of their cultural or ethnic backgrounds, feel respected, valued, and understood.

The purpose of multicultural education is to foster intercultural understanding, promote social justice, and prepare students to live and work in a diverse society. It goes beyond simply celebrating different cultures and traditions; it involves integrating diverse perspectives, knowledge, and experiences into the curriculum and teaching practices. In a colloquium of secondary school teachers, the discussion on multicultural education would likely revolve around

strategies and best practices for incorporating multicultural perspectives and content into their classrooms. The teachers would explore ways to address cultural biases, stereotypes, and prej-

udices that may exist in educational materials, and develop inclusive teaching methods that engage and empower students from different cultural backgrounds.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The study on multicultural education in classrooms, specifically within the context of a colloquium of secondary school teachers, holds several significant benefits and implications: Professional development: The colloquium serves as a platform for teachers to engage in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas related to multicultural education. It offers opportunities for professional development, allowing teachers to enhance their knowledge, skills, and strategies for implementing multicultural education in their classrooms effectively. Improved teaching practices: Through the study and discussions, teachers can gain insights into best practices and innovative approaches to multicultural education. They can learn about effective instructional strategies, resources, and assessment methods that promote inclusivity, cultural understanding, and academic achievement among students from diverse backgrounds. Increased cultural competency: The study of multicultural education enables teachers to develop a deeper understanding of different cultures, traditions, and perspectives. This knowledge enhances their cultural competency, enabling them to relate to and connect with students from diverse backgrounds. Teachers can then create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment that meets the needs of all students. Reduced cultural biases and prejudices: By engaging in the study of multicultural education, teachers become more aware of their own cultural biases and prejudices. They can identify and challenge stereotypes, misconceptions, and discrimination within the educational system, ultimately working towards a more equitable and unbiased classroom environment. Positive impact on student

outcomes: Implementing multicultural education practices has been shown to positively impact student outcomes. Students from marginalized backgrounds often experience increased academic engagement, self-esteem, and a sense of belonging when their cultural identities and experiences are acknowledged and valued. By incorporating multicultural education, teachers can create an environment that supports the academic, social, and emotional development of all students. Preparation for a diverse society: Multicultural education prepares students for life in a diverse and globalized society. By promoting intercultural understanding, respect, and collaboration, teachers help students develop the skills needed to navigate diverse workplaces, engage in respectful dialogue, and contribute positively to their communities. Social justice and equity: Multicultural education is closely tied to principles of social justice and equity. By addressing systemic inequalities and promoting inclusivity, teachers contribute to creating a more just and equitable society. The study of multicultural education within the colloquium can help raise awareness of social issues and inspire teachers to advocate for policies and practices that promote educational equity. In summary, the study of multicultural education within the colloquium of secondary school teachers has the potential to improve teaching practices, enhance cultural competency, reduce biases, and promote inclusivity. It has a positive impact on student outcomes and contributes to preparing students for a diverse world while advocating for social justice and equity within education. They actively seek to understand the cultural norms, values, and beliefs of their students and incorporate this knowledge into their instruc-

tional practices. Through this study They establish positive relationships with students and families from diverse backgrounds. They create a classroom environment that is welcoming and inclusive, and they celebrate the diversity of their students. They incorporate culturally relevant teaching strategies and materials into their instruction. They use a variety of assessment strategies to ensure that all students can demonstrate their learning. They continually reflect on their own cultural biases and work to address any inequities that may exist in their teaching practices. The results of this study would benefit the entire department of education; teachers, students, parents, and the community, in terms of getting a clear rationalization to

synthesize various activities that would address the culturally responsive teachers: through the lens of classroom advisers. Readers: This study would benefit the readers as this could give them knowledge and awareness about in culturally responsive teachers: through the lens of classroom advisers, the development of learner's knowledge that preserve and enhance a strong and inclusive social state. Lastly, the findings of this study serve as benchmark to future researchers for them to explore ways to integrate important culturally responsive teachers: through the lens of classroom advisers the development of knowledge that preserve and enhance a strong and inclusive social state for more active and participative learners.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored social learning theory proposes (Bandura, 1977). to One theoretical framework that could be relevant in examining the perceptions and experiences of teachers in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms is the social learning theory. Social learning theory proposes that individuals learn by observing others and modeling their behavior (Bandura, 1977). In the context of multicultural education, teachers may learn how to implement multicultural education by observing other teachers who have successfully implemented it in their classrooms. Another relevant theoretical framework is the critical race theory. Critical race theory emphasizes the role of race and racism in shaping social institutions and practices (Delgado Stefancic, 2017). In the context of multicultural education, critical race theory can help to uncover the ways in which race and racism affect the implementation of multicultural education in diverse classrooms and how teachers can address these issues. The cultural responsiveness theory is also relevant to this topic. This theory

emphasizes the importance of understanding the cultural backgrounds of students and incorporating their cultural perspectives into the curriculum (Gay, 2010). In the context of multicultural education, cultural responsiveness theory can guide teachers in creating an inclusive and culturally responsive classroom environment that values the diversity of their students. Lastly, the transformative learning theory can also be useful in examining teachers' experiences in implementing multicultural education. Transformative learning theory proposes that individuals can undergo a transformative experience by reflecting critically on their assumptions and beliefs (Mezirow, 1991). In the context of multicultural education, teachers may undergo a transformative learning experience as they reflect on their own biases and beliefs and learn to value the diversity of their students. Overall, these theoretical frameworks provide useful insights into the perceptions and experiences of teachers in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms and can guide future research in this area.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter, the researcher introduced the philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research participants, data collections, data analysis, ethical considerations, role of the researcher, and trustworthiness.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—It was assumed that all participants answered interview questions honestly and to the best of their abilities. It was further assumed that the sample used for this study was representative of in-depth and focus group interviews on a face-to-face manner as a medium of communication. These assumptions have been articulated throughout the last 20 years in the various SAGE Handbooks of Qualitative Research (Denzin Lincoln, 1994, 2000, 2005, 2011) and as the “axiomatic” issues advanced by Guba and Lincoln (1988) as the guiding philosophy behind qualitative research. These beliefs have been called paradigms (Lincoln, 1985) philosophical assumptions, epistemologies, and ontologies (Crotty, 1998); broadly conceived research methodologies (Neuman, 2000); and alternative knowledge claims (Creswell, 2014). There are beliefs about ontology (the nature of reality), epistemology (what counts as knowledge and how knowledge claims are justified), axiology (the role of values in research), and methodology (the process of research). In this discussion, I will first discuss each of these philosophical assumptions, detail how they might be used and written into qualitative research, and then link them to different interpretive frameworks that

operate at a more specific level in the process of research. Ontology. The issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics. When researchers conduct qualitative research, they are embracing the idea of teacher’s perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms. Different researchers embrace different realities, as do the individuals being studied and the readers of a qualitative study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 1994). Epistemology. Conducting a qualitative study means that the researcher tries to get as close as possible to the participants being studied. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. The very reason why I chose these high school teachers as my participants is because I knew them for quite a long time. This is how knowledge is known through the subjective experiences of

people. It becomes important, then, to conduct studies in the “field,” where the participants live and work, these are important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the “field” or get to know the participants, the more they “know what they know” from firsthand information. For example, good phenomenology requires a prolonged stay at the research site (Wolcott, 2008a). In short, the researcher tries to minimize the “distance” or “objective separateness” (Guba Lincoln, 1988, p. 94) between himself or herself and those being researched. Axiology. This assumption characterizes qualitative research. How does the researcher implement this assumption in practice? In a qualitative

study, the inquirers admit the value-laden nature of the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. This means that the result of this study will be shared with the school where I am currently working. We say that they “position themselves” in a study. In an interpretive biography, for example, the researcher’s presence is apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 1989a). I believe that I am more qualified to conduct this study since I have ample experience teaching in junior high school.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The researcher made these qualitative assumptions that consist of the methods used in the process of qualitative research (Creswell 2003). The procedures used by the researcher are inductive and are based on the researcher’s own experience in collecting and analyzing data. The research here is the product of the values of the researcher. Through an inductive approach, raw textual data is condensed into a brief, summary format. Clear links are established between research objectives and summary findings derived from raw data. A framework of the underlying structure of experiences or processes that are evident from the raw data is developed. A phenomenological study describes the meaning of lived experiences of individuals about a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2003) was used in this study. A phenomenological study intends to understand and describe an event from the point of view of the participants. A key characteristic of this approach is to study how members of a group or community interpret themselves, the world, and life around them

(Mertens, 2005). The purpose of this study was to explore teachers’ perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms, related to building background, student interactions, and application, to meet the needs of learners as well as the possible challenges experienced by teachers when implementing these practices. Collectively, these results may provide foundational information to guide the district in addressing the local issue. Administrators might benefit from this information as it might enable them to make informed decisions about what support is needed for teachers in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms. In addition, this study was to discover the teachers’ perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms in selected junior high schools appear to have experienced towards teachers’ perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms, specifically in the areas of building background knowledge, interactions, and application.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—

In the next section, the specific details of the research procedures will be described, so future researchers can generalize the results from this study to other situations. Extensive and careful descriptions of the time, place, context, and culture of the study will be thoroughly discussed to develop transferability, which is the qualitative parallel to external validity in post-positivist research (Mertens, 2005). This section will: (a) discuss the interview approach; (b) explain the role of the researcher; and lastly, (c) describe the sampling method and ethical considerations. Semi-Structured Interviews. Patton (2015) proposes researchers conduct interviews to learn the things they cannot directly observe. Qualitative interviewing is not used to get answers to questions, but to understand the experiences of the participants and the meaning they make of that experience (Seidman, 1988). Generally, qualitative studies use unstructured, open-ended interviews, because they allow for the most flexibility and responsiveness to emerging issues for both the participants and interviewer; however, the use of semi-structured interviews is not uncommon and used when the researcher seeks to obtain specific more focused information (Schwandt, 2001). Semi-structured interviews combine the flexibility of unstructured, open-ended interviews with directionality and an agenda to produce focused, qualitative, textual data (Schensul, LeCompte, 71 1999). This

study collected data using semi-structured interviews to explore how the junior high school teachers describe the teachers' perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms, teachers experience in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms. To ensure that the same information was collected from all the participants, an interview guide was used. The interview guide included open-ended questions and topics to help structure the interview, but when needed, the interviewer also explored, probed, and asked additional questions to clarify and expand on a particular topic. The interview guide helped make interviewing across several different participants more systematic and comprehensive by defining in advance the issues to be explored (Patton, 2015). The open-ended questions were framed in a way, so the participants could represent their views and perspectives in their own words and terms, in addition to taking the questions in any direction that they chose (Patton, 2015). Since qualitative research studies subjects in their natural setting, all interviews except one took place using a face-to-face format at a time convenient for the participants. All interview sessions were tape-recorded for the purposes of transcription. When needed, the researcher used follow-up interviews after transcription to clarify meaning or explore areas in more depth.

2.4. Research Participants—The target population for this study will be the twelve (12) participants from the line-up of public high school faculty, a junior high school unit who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. The selected participants will join for an in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). The researcher considered the faculty from selected public schools who are still teaching. From this population, a sample of twelve (12) junior high school teachers was pur-

posefully selected. The researcher will use purposive sampling (also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling) wherein it is a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. This survey sampling method requires researchers to have prior knowledge about the purpose of their studies so that they can properly choose and approach eligible participants to be conducted (Denzin, 2017). The participants of this

study are the junior high school teachers from the selected public schools in Division of Davao

Oriental. Below is the simple description of the participants:

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical standards are required in conducting research; thus, this phenomenological research adheres to the principles of Belmont Report (1979) which strictly observed the principles of respect of persons, beneficence, and justice. Specifically, this study was subjected to the evaluation of the College where the researcher is studying, Inc. – Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) for the full board review of the ethical aspects of the investigation as regards the dimensions of research ethics that include social value, informed consent, vulnerability issues, risk-benefit ratio, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, qualification of the researchers, adequacy of facilities and community involvement. Social Value. The researcher investigated and carefully analyze one of the pressing problems in our educational system. Also, this research regarding teachers’ perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms. This study is expected to provide important information in recognizing the extent and type of experiences that the basic education teachers experienced. The findings of this study can provide more insights among basic education teachers and basic education students to maintain quality teaching and learning. The researcher is hopeful that the output of the study is relevant not only to the participants but to the school. The result of the study would be presented in the local, national, and even international fora and if given a chance to publish in an international publication. Informed consent. In this study, informed consent was secured from all the participants who were involved in the study. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the study to twelve (12) junior high school

teachers. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The participants had sufficient information and an adequate understanding of both the proposal and the implications of their participation in the study. Codes were assigned to individuals in the data presented. Every page of the transcriptions of the in-depth interview and focus group discussions were signed by the researcher to attest that the key informant interviews were done with the consent of informants. In addition, the informants were accorded with the needed respect. The researcher made it a point that the form must bear the signature of the participant or agreement which would imply that she participated in the study voluntarily. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The researcher protected the participants from being deceived, threatened, and/or forced to participate. The researcher treated them with the highest respect. Thus, they were informed ahead that they may withdraw their participation in the study and if ever inconvenience was felt during the interview and in answering the questionnaire, they would be given the chance to raise their concern and opt to cancel the activity. Although the participants were of legal age, 18 years old and above, they were still vulnerable because the researcher is a junior high school teachers Banaybanay District, Division of Davao Oriental, as one of the selected research locales of the study. Teachers were treated with utmost respect so as for them not to be vulnerable while participating in this study. The researcher considered the basic junior high school teachers as participants in this study because they are mature enough to decide for themselves to partake in this study or not. Risks-Benefit Safety. A careful assessment of foreseeable risks, burdens, and benefits to the participants was made. The questionnaire

that the researcher administered did not contain any degrading, discriminating, or unacceptable language that was offensive to the participants so that the risks were avoided. An extra careful approach was used in collecting the data so that irrelevant and confidential details were rejected. The study did not involve any high-risk situation that the participants may experience in their social and emotional needs. Further, this study ensured that the potential benefits of the participants were greater than the potential harm. The results of this study would benefit the entire department of education; teachers, students, parents, and the community, in terms of getting a clear rationalization to synthesize various activities that would address the teachers' perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms. Practically the researcher identified only minimal risks if not negligible regarding physical harm or discomfort that they may experience during the conduct of the study. Specifically, whatever might cause adverse effects on personal relationships, loss of status, privacy, or time of the respondents were taken into consideration in the planning stage of the conduct of the study so that such things would be minimized if not prevented fully. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The current study ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the information of the respondents. The researcher adhered to the principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 or Republic Act 10173 which mandates transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in the collection, retention, and processing of personal information (Congress of the Philippines, 2012). This act protected the fundamentals of human rights on the privacy of information which ensured the free flow of information that promotes innovation and growth. The researcher protected the respondent/participants' right to privacy wherein their responses were given with the highest respect. Unless required by the law, the confidentiality of information shall always be observed.

Other personal information will not be asked in the study to safeguard their identities and to enable them to participate without any fear of the revelation of involvement in the study. Any information will be taken with utmost care to ensure the anonymity of the data sources and de-identification of any personal information that would be shared. Such names and identities were protected by using a pseudonym. The tracing of the information of these codes was reflected in an archival log. Hence, personal names were not used in the tracing of identification. Written responses, if any, were captured through a camera. Recordings were saved and documents were kept in one single place that is protected or encrypted. Justice. In this study, justice requires an equitable distribution of both the burdens and the benefits of participation in research. There was a fair selection in the choice of population, sampling, and assignments. Provision of appropriate care to research participants regardless of their economic status, gender, race, or creed was provided. With this, the researcher assured the respondents who were involved were appropriate for the study. The researcher provided just compensation and reimbursement for data used and costs incurred by the participants. The participants were adequately informed on the objectives of the study before they were involved in the process. It was emphasized that they were the source of data and encouraged to give their honest answers in the survey questionnaire. In return, they were the priority on the benefits for the possible offshoots of the study findings. Transparency. To be ethical, all the parties need to be transparent by making sure that the process, the nature of the study, and the extent of participation are clear and understandable to the participants. The researcher was transparent about the aspects of the study, especially that information that has bearing on the decision of participants to give or withhold their informed consent. The participants can access and scru-

tinize the findings of the study if the findings were scientifically valid and have significant implications on the participant's well-being. The researcher assured that the study was conveyed in full scope and with accuracy. Specifically, in qualitative data analysis, findings were identified, confirmed, or rejected accordingly. Moreover, data transcriptions were presented to the participants to attain precision. Consequently, the researcher ensured the reasonable availability and accessibility of the research outcomes to department of education; teachers; students; parents, and the community. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher is ultimately responsible and accountable for the research. For the research to be carried out with necessary skills and knowledge. I am aware of the limits of personal competence in research. With my experience as a junior high school teacher in one of the public schools in Banaybanay District, Division of Davao Oriental. I attended several research-related seminars and training which I consider as an asset in conducting this study with the assistance of my adviser and colleagues, readings from various books and literature, fulfilling my duties and responsibilities at RMC as a junior high school teacher and the supervision of RMC-REC, I acquired the knowledge and skills needed to conduct the research. Also, the supervision and direction of his adviser, as well the panelists helped improve the research study. The researcher's adviser is an expert in this study. Therefore, the adviser is a big help to complete the study with the quality of the content. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher is adequately equipped with the budget and equipment needed for the conduct of the study. This is to ensure that the researcher has the best facilities in the completion of the research. The laptop, printer, internet connection, and other facilities needed are personally owned by the researcher making the facilities adequately and readily available. Furthermore, the library resources, both non-online and online, are readily available such as books, and google. In addition, if possible, google meet was the form used in gathering the data. Aside from the enumerated resources, some experts provided the researcher with the guidance needed in the conduct of this research like the adviser, RMC-Research Ethics Committee, and panel members who are also the expert validators. Community Involvement. The researcher is engaged with communities like the Public Schools academic community, teachers, parents, and the basic education students since I am a teacher in one of the public schools in Banaybanay District, Division of Davao Oriental is composed of quite diverse people; thus, the researcher is sensitive to and respects the cultural, traditional, and religious practices of the community. The RMC graduate school helped in correcting, validating, and revising the manuscript of the current study. The RMC graduate school provided directions, based on its research standards and practices to the researcher. The involvement of the junior high school teachers, students, parents, participated in the development of the questionnaire through the output of the first phase of the study. The guide questions served as the instrument in gathering qualitative data in the second phase. On the other hand, proper protocol and seeking approval from the principal of the public schools as my target participants was observed. Moreover, the significant personas in the public-school organizational landscape and other stakeholders may benefit from the output of the study because they are the recipients of the data regarding knowledge about the project-based learning instructional practices for education.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher—*

The primary instrument in qualitative research is human, so all observations and analyses are filtered through that human being's worldview, values, and perspectives (Merriam, 1998). Therefore, researchers must reflect on the values, assumptions, beliefs, and biases that they bring to their research (Mertens, 2020). This is important, because when another researcher looks at the data collected, they may sort and interpret the findings differently (Miles Huberman, 1994). Bias must be controlled if the results of a study are to seem truthful (Locke, Spirduso Silverman, 2000). A researcher can achieve an unbiased attitude through the process of self-disclosure, where the researcher considers the research problem about their background and attitudes before conducting the interviews (Patton, 2020). Locke, Spirduso, and Silverman (2000) suggest when an attempt is made to create an awareness of the researcher's assumptions, it can have a positive effect on the research process. In the next section, the researcher will explain her background, biases, values, and personal interests about the re-

search topic and process (Creswell, 2003). Self-Disclosure. I believed that my experiences as a junior high school teacher prevented me from being a neutral party within this study. I bring to the study my personal experiences from accepting my co-faculty in the school year 2020-2023 and the assumptions about helping them in their academic and personal needs. To disclose my professional experiences, it is evident that I have several years in terms of experiences meeting with the teachers in the high school that influence my background, biases, and values. Although every effort will be made to ensure objectivity in this study, my biases as a researcher may shape the way I analyze and interpret the data. In the data analysis section, several methods to address this limitation will be described. Although my experience is limited, my personal experiences as a junior high school teacher are also a positive and valuable resource in this study. Miles and Huberman (2020) propose that an empathetic understanding of the participants and the setting by the researcher is a characteristic of qualitative research.

2.7. *Data Collection*—Prior to the conduct of data gathering, I must ask for the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of College where the researcher is studying to pursue the study. After the permissions are approved by the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principals of the target participants, the researcher will talk to the participants to acquaint them with the purpose of the study. I will agree with the participants on the most convenient date and time for the conduct of the interview. The researchers set to schedule the data gathering and administering the research tool this academic year 2023-2024 at the month of May. To start the interview, I will ask the participants to read the respondents' consent and to affix their signature on the consent paper after they are oriented of the purpose of the study

and respectively agree on the terms and conditions. The researcher will emphasize to the respondents that they are allowed to ask question for clarify any matter regarding the study and ask their consent to record the course of the conversation with the assurance that everything shall be dealt with utmost confidentiality. Through in-depth interview, I will be able to gather the feelings, reactions, observations, and experiences of the teachers in their conduct towards sleep deprivation related to personality development of pupils. The interview will include the gathering of information as to obstacles and challenges that the teachers encounter with the home visitations. I will likewise aim to obtain substantial information exploring the use of science simulations in grade 5 class considering the teacher perspectives to personality devel-

opment of pupils and the interventions that help bridge the risk of understanding and making science subject into more realistic experiences for the pupils. In analyzing the data gathered, the participant's narratives will be transcribed. According to Koontz and Weinrich (2000), the process and narratives do not need to be transcribed verbatim if the essence of what the participants were communicating has been caught in the transcription. Individual transcriptions of the interview will be validated by the respective participants. To verify and revalidate the data gathered, the researcher will conduct focus group discussion to validate and triangulate the information gathered. Corrections may be made according to the participants' feedback to ensure that the meaning will be conveyed in the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussion will be collected. Field notes will be used to record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and will be based on an interview guide. Data will be generated through field notes, a voice recorder or cellphone videos, during the interviews with participants. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedule. The interval between interviews was on average one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions will also be made to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over attributes of high-quality. In a qualitative phenomenological study, research data involved the researcher spending as much time as possible within the teachers at the high schools to gain an in-depth understanding of the junior high school teachers in their everyday lives. Participant observations of the behaviors, beliefs, traditions, culture, social and emotional interactions were recorded at the end of each day in a journal. Where applicable in-depth interviews were conducted in field settings and were either recorded and transcribed, and/or summarized in the journal. As an active participant in the research process, the researcher constantly evaluated her role, her relationship with participants, and applied this to develop an understanding and interpretation of the basic education teacher's social and emotional worlds (Unger, 2005). This resulted in an evolving research process both in terms of the direction and type of data derived and in terms of a personal transformation for the researcher (Parker, 2005). The evolution of the research as a relational transformation between a researcher with openness for a new experience and a community of participants cannot be over-emphasized. The results of which could not have been foreseen at the inception of this study (Parker, 2005). As noted earlier, the location of the study is an academic institution that experienced changes in its way of teaching. The researcher already spent several years as a junior high school teacher, and I have a great chance to gather demographic information and to meet as many of the locals as possible. Also, it was hoped that an initial understanding of the community culture could be gained through participant observation. All participants signed an informed consent form before being interviewed. Questionnaires will be translated by the researcher to the language commonly used by the participants. Data collection was multimodal. According to Yin (2003), the main characteristic of phenomenological qualitative research is that it employs various data collection methods to ensure the trustworthiness of the report. Multiple data sources promote a

clearer understanding of the data being studied (Creswell, 2008, 2009; Glesne, 2011; Merriam, 2009). Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussion will be collected. Field notes will be used to record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and will be based on an interview guide. Data will be generated through field notes, a voice recorder or cellphone videos, dur-

ing the interviews with participants. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedule. The interval between interviews was on average one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions will also be made to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over attributes of high-quality.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—Qualitative data analysis begins with the process of organizing, reducing, and describing the collected data (Schwandt, 2001). Unlike quantitative analysis, there are no prescribed formulas for qualitative analysis. Marshall and Rossman (2006) remind researchers that qualitative analysis does not proceed linearly and is not neat. However, good practice and procedures enhance the credibility of qualitative research. In this last section, the data analysis procedures will be explained, and the steps taken to ensure the results from this study are credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic will be thoroughly described. To guide the data analysis, the researcher used the seven phases of data analysis described by Marshall and Rossman (2006) to reduce data, create manageable pieces, allow for interpretation, and find meaning in the words of the participants. The seven phases included: (a) organizing the data; (b) immersion in the data; (c) generating categories and themes; (d) coding the data; (e) offering interpretations through analytic memos; and (f) searching for alternative understandings (Marshall Rossman, 2006). Data analysis first begins with organizing the data. The organization of the data involved keeping information provided by each participant separate and in se-

quence with the order of the interviews. The process of organizing the data allowed it to remain manageable, easily accessible, and readily available. The digital audio files from the interviews were carefully transcribed into written form. Electronic folders were established to create an organization for the data collected from each participant. Next, the researcher became familiar with the data through extensive reading of the interviews to gain an understanding of the content. This involved reading through the interviews at least three times. Following Hatch's (2002) recommendations for qualitative analysis, the researcher created a sheet of notes for each participant. The summary sheets were a quick way to refer to the original data as the data analysis continued (Hatch, 2002). After the initial readings, Hatch (2002) recommends researchers read data through completely with one typology in mind. Patton (2015) defines typologies as classification systems made up of categories that divide some aspects of the world into parts. According to Hatch (2002), typologies are generated from theory, common sense, or research objectives. For this study, the researcher used the typologies or themes from the literature review as the constructs through which to view the data. After reading through

the data with each constructor typology in mind, the researcher coded the data into five categories from the literature by taking excerpts of text from the data and identifying it within a particular category. After everything was coded, the researcher read through the data again while writing analytic memos on her thoughts and insights and began the process of offering interpretations. During this stage, the researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the teachers' instructional experiences through pulling salient themes, reoccur-

ring ideas, and patterns of belief that resonated collectively throughout the interviews. The offering of interpretations began following the emergence of themes in the data. Marshall and Rossman (2006) believe this part of the data analysis brings meaning to the themes and categories and allows the researcher to develop links between the interviews. The researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in teachers' perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—It was shown in analytical frame work in the teachers perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms in high school classrooms is a structure for the best teaching instructions and pedagogy , carried along of learners personality and inclination for growth development which most effective in teaching learning process, also the interest of learners were affects from teachers demands, and parents supervision as what their experience to be divulge and bring new insight and hope to upcoming similar situation or case. The experiences were analyzed to bring out their insight and feelings to make a difference in the educational system. Both aims to provide information on unfolding story of teachers towards teacher's perceptions and experiences in implementing

multicultural education in diverse classrooms. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed in searching for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. Following the signing of consent forms, teachers' perceptions, and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms using semi-structured in-depth interviews. Data was organized and analyzed. The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in taking circle to ensure that we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis (Mazuwelics, 2018).

Thematic Content Analysis. This was used in interpreting the responses made by the key participants in determining the lessons and insights derived from the views of teacher's perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms. Their responses were processed and conducted through analyses. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back

and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interview may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes that may be found among the responses to each question. In this phase, the researcher may use thematic analysis

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

in analyzing the gathered data. Their responses were processed and conducted through analysis. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher’s interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interview may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes that may be found among the responses to each question. Environmental Triangulation. Triangulation analysis is a tool developed by Margaret Schuler to help advocates perform a strategic analysis of the issues they are working on. The tool looks at three different aspects: con-

tent, structure, and culture. Triangular analysis is a technique for both analyzing and finding answers to a problem, structured around structure, content and culture in the policy system was done through transcribing, member checking and triangulation. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in taking circle to ensure that we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis. To achieve a truthful and productive result in a qualitative study, the researcher must possess trustworthiness and credibility. With this, the researcher religiously followed the requirements (Mazuwelics, 2018).

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Qualitative research does not claim to be replicable. The researcher purposefully avoids controlling the research conditions and concentrates on recording the complexity of situational contexts and interrelations as they occur naturally (Marshall Rossman, 2006). This study took many extra steps to ensure the results from the data analysis were credible, transferable, de-

pendable, and authentic. Credibility. Mertens (2020) defines credibility as a correspondence between the way a participant perceived social constructs and the way the researcher portrays the participant’s viewpoints. To ensure credibility in this study, the researcher used persistent observation that allowed for interviews that were long enough to identify salient issues (Mertens, 2020). The researcher also moni-

tored her developing constructions and documented any changes she experienced from the beginning of the study to the end in the analytic memos. This procedure began with the researcher's disclosure of values, beliefs, and experiences that connect her to the topic of teachers' perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms. Transferability. Establishing transferability provides the degree to which the results can be generalized to other situations. The researcher kept an audit trail, which is a meticulous record of the research process so other researchers can recapture steps and the same conclusions. Extensive and careful descriptions of the time, place, context, and culture of the study were kept developing a thick description (Mertens, 2020). Not only was the data kept, but also the evidence of how the data were reduced, analyzed, and synthesized as well as the process notes that reflect the ongoing inner thoughts, hunches, and reactions of the researcher (New-

ton Rudestam, 2001). Conformability. "Conformability means that the data and the interpretation are not figments of the researcher's imagination" (Mertens, 2005, p. 257). In this study, the data gathered will be analyzed and interpreted properly to arrive at a convincing theme that would further discuss the importance of teacher's perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms. To establish conformability, the researcher kept track of the qualitative data so it can be tracked to its source in the interviews. Authenticity. To establish authenticity within the study, the researcher presents a balanced view of all perspectives, values, and beliefs. As a researcher, I must avoid bias in gathering the data. This study teachers' perceptions and experiences in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms used peer debriefing to play the role is asking tough questions about the data collection, data analysis, and data interpretations (Newton Rudestam, 2001).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results of the data analysis and the discussion of the results of the study, focused on multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, information was gathered to examine on what are the lived experiences of teachers in multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. What is the lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms? How do teachers cope with challenges of multi-cultural education? What educational management insight can be drawn from the findings of the study? Merged with the theme. Before I begin my discussion, I would like to establish the symbols I used as I present the quotations based on the responses of the participants of the study. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, I used codes to refer to participants of the research question. Their responses were contained and bounded around the three (3) research questions of the study. Moreover, the responses of both the IDI and the FGD participants were transcribed in verbatim manner, translated into English, encoded, and summarized in matrix form, which led to a schema. The first objective of this study is the experiences of teachers on multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' participants of the multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. The transcripts of participants of focus grouped discussion are as follows: Answer to research Question and connected to first theme, which is addressing challenges.

3.1. *The lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms—*

Research questions number 1 what is the lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms?

3.1.1. Addressing Challenges—First, concerns are what are the lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms. Merged with the theme, saturated from the data of participants, highlighted the addressing challenges. The theme mentioned demands the learner needs in learning, supporting effective implementation on exploring the multicultural education in classrooms considered the colloquium of secondary school teachers. Participants frequently expressed concern for various responsibilities competing for the limited resources of time and energy. Therefore, based on the research questions of the study dealt on multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, with the specific theme addressing challenges. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study what the multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, with the specific theme addressing challenges. The statement reflects a what they lived experience as teachers in diverse classrooms. The use of multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, students to take ownership of their learning, encouraging independent exploration, and fostering a sense of scientific inquiry. Incorporating multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers enables teachers to bridge the gap between theory and practice, allowing students to apply scientific principles in realistic and interactive virtual scenarios in multicultural education in classrooms considering the colloquium of secondary school teachers. These statements provide insights into the experiences, dedication, and values of teachers in diverse classrooms, showcasing their commitment to creating inclusive and empowering educational environments. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt what the content or statements highlight the teachers' reflections, experiences, and dedication in creating inclusive and transformative learning environments for students from diverse backgrounds. These statements reflect the teachers' appreciation, growth, and dedication to creating inclusive and empowering educational environments that celebrate diversity. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt what the use of these statements reflects the teachers' commitment, growth, and the profound impact of teaching in diverse classrooms, emphasizing the importance of inclusivity, cultural responsiveness, and fostering a supportive learning environment for all students. Diversity and multiculturalism in higher education: This journal article explores the challenges and opportunities of promoting diversity and multiculturalism in higher education. It discusses the role of teachers in creating a culturally responsive learning environment, and the challenges that teachers face in implementing multicultural education in diverse classrooms Nieto, S. (2019). As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on what they lived experiences of teachers in are exploring the These statements demonstrate how teachers cope with the challenges of multicultural education in diverse classrooms by continually learning, adapting their strategies, fostering inclusive environments, and collaborating with others. They highlight the importance of cultural competency, communication, and creating a supportive and enriching learning experience for all students. Teacher education for diversity: Critical perspectives: This book examines the

role of teacher education in preparing teachers for teaching in diverse classrooms. It provides critical perspectives on the existing teacher edu-

3.1.2. Addressing Intersectionality—The theme mentioned demands the learner needs in learning, supporting effective implementation on exploring the multicultural education in classrooms considered the colloquium of secondary school teachers. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on what they lived experiences of teachers in are exploring the use of these statements highlight the ways in which teachers draw upon their teacher preparation experiences to cope with the challenges of multicultural education. They underscore the importance of self-reflection, cultural competence, inclusive teaching strategies, and ongoing professional growth in creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment for students from diverse backgrounds, theme addressing intersectionality. Culturally responsive teaching: Theory, research, and practice: This book provides an overview of culturally responsive teaching, a pedagogical approach that seeks to promote student achievement and engagement by integrating students' cultural backgrounds into the teaching and learning process. It offers practical strategies for implementing culturally responsive teaching in diverse classrooms Ladson-Billings, G. (2019). As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on what These statements reflect the perspectives of secondary school teachers engaging in a colloquium focused on multicultural education and culturally responsive teaching. They highlight the benefits and importance of embracing diverse cultural identities, fostering inclusivity, and creating an empowering learning environment for all students. Recent studies emphasize the importance of considering and addressing these intersecting identities in the design

and implementation of multicultural education. Researchers argue that an inclusive approach to multicultural education should go beyond a single-dimensional focus on cultural or ethnic diversity and should encompass a broader understanding of diverse identities and experiences. (De Matthews, 2019). As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on these statements reflect the perspectives of secondary school teachers engaging in a colloquium focused on multicultural education and culturally responsive teaching. They emphasize the benefits of embracing diverse perspectives, fostering inclusivity, and promoting a positive and empowering learning environment for all students. Cunningham, and Hong (2019) titled "Addressing Intersectionality in Teacher Education: The Role of Multicultural Education" highlights the need for teacher educators and practitioners to incorporate intersectionality into their curriculum and pedagogical practices. The study emphasizes that educators should recognize and address the complexities of students' identities and experiences to create inclusive and equitable classrooms. Another relevant study is by Cho, DeCastro-Ambrosetti, and Kim (2020) titled "Teachers' Understandings and Practices of Intersectionality in the Multicultural Education Classroom. This study explores how teachers perceive and incorporate intersectionality into their multicultural education practices. The findings highlight the importance of teachers developing a critical understanding of intersectionality and integrating it into their instructional strategies to promote social justice and inclusion. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on what These statements highlight the importance of teacher professional development in multicultural education and how

it contributes to creating inclusive and equitable classrooms. They emphasize the role of continuous learning, collaboration, self-reflection, and the exchange of ideas in fostering a supportive and culturally responsive educational environment. Making Asia relevant to students It is important for teachers to understand the intent driving the inclusion of 'Asia and Australia's engagement with Asia' as a cross-curriculum priority, so that it can be addressed in ways that are not only consistent with the aims of the cross-curriculum priority outlined by ACARA, but also inclusive of the ever-changing diversity of experiences and perspectives of students within Australian classrooms (ACARA, 2019). However, Elaine, (2020) understood this to mean

3.1.3. Addressing Diversity—The concern is what are the lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms. Merged with the theme, saturated from the data of participants, highlighted the addressing diversity. The theme mentioned demands the learner needs in learning, supporting effective implementation on exploring the multicultural education in classrooms considered the colloquium of secondary school teachers. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study what they lived experiences of teachers in are These statements reflect the perspectives of secondary school teachers engaging in a colloquium focused on multicultural education in classrooms and the significance of teacher professional development. They highlight the importance of collaborative learning, reflection, cultural competence, and the ongoing pursuit of knowledge to create inclusive and culturally responsive learning environments. By The definitive goals of culturally relevant teaching are to build students' cultural competence and sociopolitical consciousness and increase student achievement while critiquing the norms that delimit what counts as achievement. Changing Demographics: The increas-

that these specific spheres must be explicitly addressed through the texts she selected to address the cross-curriculum priority in her classroom. She shared that it would be unethical in an English classroom to push a political and economic agenda of the government. These studies demonstrate the significance of recent research on intersectionality in multicultural education and highlight the need for educators to consider the intersecting identities and experiences of their students to create more inclusive and equitable classrooms. Exploring more recent literature in the field will provide further insights and specific references to support your study.

ing cultural diversity within educational settings necessitates a comprehensive understanding of multicultural education. With shifting demographics and growing numbers of students from diverse backgrounds, it is crucial to examine the challenges and strategies that can enhance inclusive and equitable learning environments (Gorski, 2021; Lee, 2018). As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on what they lived experiences of teachers in are exploring the use of the colloquium on teacher professional development in multicultural education brings together secondary school teachers to discuss the importance of embracing cultural diversity and implementing effective strategies for creating inclusive classrooms. This content explores the value of multicultural education and the role of ongoing teacher professional development in fostering equitable and culturally responsive learning environments, theme educational equity, teacher preparation, enhancing learning outcomes. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on what they lived experiences of teachers in are exploring the use of the colloquium on teacher profes-

Fig. 3. Thematic Framework of lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms

sional development in multicultural education brings together secondary school teachers to discuss the importance of embracing cultural diversity and implementing effective strategies for creating inclusive classrooms. This content explores the value of multicultural education and the role of ongoing teacher professional development in fostering equitable and culturally responsive learning environments, theme educational equity, teacher preparation, enhancing learning outcomes. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt what they lived experiences of teachers in Teacher professional development plays a crucial role in preparing educators to effectively implement multicultural education strategies. Ongoing professional de-

velopment opportunities provide teachers with the knowledge, skills, and resources necessary to create culturally responsive classrooms. Gay, (2018). Through workshops, seminars, and collaborative learning experiences, teachers can enhance their cultural competence, expand their pedagogical approaches, and address the specific needs of diverse learners (Villegas Lucas, 2020). The colloquium serves as a platform for teachers to exchange experiences, share best practices, and engage in critical discussions about multicultural education. Collaborative colloquiums enable teachers to learn from one another, gain fresh perspectives, and inspire innovative approaches to classroom instruction (Darling-Hammond et al., 20197).

3.1.4. *Low student involvement*—The second objective of this study is the teacher’s coping mechanism with the challenges in teachers’ cope with challenges of multi-cultural education. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the

teachers’ participants of the teachers’ cope with challenges of multi-cultural education. The transcripts of participants of focus grouped discussion are as follows: Answer to research Question teachers’ experience teachers’ cope with challenges of multi-cultural education and connected to the first theme, which is educational equity. Participants frequently expressed con-

cern for various responsibilities competing for the limited resources of time and energy. Therefore, based on the research questions of the study dealt on how teachers cope with the challenges in cope with challenges of multi-cultural education and connected to the first theme educational equity. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on how teachers cope with the challenges in using multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers with the specific theme Addressing challenges, addressing intersectionality, addressing diversity. To support the content discussed during the colloquium, teachers can reference scholarly articles, research studies, and educational frameworks. Some notable resources include the works of James Banks, Geneva Gay, and Sonia Nieto, who have made significant contributions to the field of multicultural education. Teachers can also explore

3.1.5. Educational Equity—The colloquium on teacher professional development in multicultural education provides a valuable opportunity for secondary school teachers to deepen their understanding of multicultural education, share experiences, and collaborate on effective strategies. By embracing ongoing professional development and incorporating research-based practices, teachers can create inclusive and culturally responsive classrooms that celebrate diversity, promote social justice, and foster meaningful learning experiences for all students. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on how teachers cope with the challenges in using multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. Multicultural education involves creating inclusive learning environments that respect

3.1.6. Teacher Preparation—

research published in reputable journals such as *Multicultural Education Review*, *Teaching and Teacher Education*, and *Educational Researcher* (Holland, 2021). Student involvement is one of the many factors in class work. It is expected that students must do their performance tasks at the highest expected outcomes, however, this is not the case in some of the students under study. Some of the students did not bother to perform their class tasks as expected. It turned out that only a few of the group members were performing well, other students remained as audience during the conduct of the activities. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on how teachers cope with the challenges in using multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, with the specific theme educational equity, teacher preparation, enhancing learning outcomes.

and value the diverse cultural backgrounds of students. It aims to promote equity, social justice, and cultural competence among educators and learners. Multicultural education enhances students' academic achievement, engagement, and self-esteem by providing them with opportunities to learn about and appreciate different cultures (Gay, 2019). The second objective of this study is the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges in teachers' cope with challenges of multi-cultural education. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' participants of the teachers' cope with challenges of multi-cultural education. The transcripts of participants of focus grouped discussion are as follows:

Participants frequently expressed concern for various responsibilities competing for the limited resources of time and energy. Therefore, based on the research questions of the study dealt on how teachers cope with the challenges in cope with challenges of multi-cultural education and connected to the second theme teacher preparation. These statements highlight how teachers draw upon their teacher preparation experiences to cope with the challenges of multicultural education. They emphasize the importance of reflective practices, collaboration, cultural responsiveness, and ongoing professional development to support the needs of diverse learners effectively. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on how teachers cope with the challenges in using multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, with the specific theme teacher preparation. To continuous learning and growth opportunities that empower educators to improve their instructional practices, pedagogical strategies, and cultural responsiveness. Professional development programs help teachers develop cultural compe-

tence by increasing their understanding of diverse cultures, challenging biases, and adopting inclusive teaching strategies (Gay, 2022). Ongoing professional development equips teachers with effective instructional practices for multicultural education, such as culturally relevant pedagogy, culturally responsive teaching, and differentiated instruction (Banks, 2020). As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on how teachers cope with the challenges multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. The challenges of the colloquium serve as a platform for secondary school teachers to engage in collaborative learning, share experiences, and exchange best practices in multicultural education. Teachers discuss and explore research-based strategies and frameworks for integrating multicultural education into their instructional practices. The colloquium encourages teachers to reflect on their own cultural identities, biases, and teaching practices, fostering a deeper understanding of the impact of culture on education (Ladson-Billings, 2019).

3.1.7. Enhancing Learning Outcomes— Teachers address the challenge of limited time by carefully planning and integrating the colloquium on teacher professional development in multicultural education provides a space for secondary school teachers to deepen their understanding, share experiences, and explore effective strategies. By embracing ongoing professional development and incorporating research-informed approaches, teachers can create inclusive classrooms that celebrate diversity, promote cultural competence, and foster positive learning experiences for all students. To overcome the challenge of students passively consuming information during science simulations, teachers facilitate active learning by incorpo-

rating reflective tasks. They encourage students to analyze their findings, compare results, and draw conclusions, promoting a deeper understanding of scientific concepts and fostering critical thinking skills. Teachers cope with the challenge of adapting multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on how teachers cope with the challenges multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, with the specific theme enhancing learning outcomes. To cope with the challenge of assessing student learning during multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium

of secondary school teachers, teachers employ various formative assessment strategies. They use observation, questioning, and analysis of student interactions within the simulations to gauge understanding, provide timely feedback, and make instructional adjustments. To address the challenge of limited technical proficiency among grade 5 students, teachers offer explicit instruction and scaffolded support in using science simulations. They provide step-by-step demonstrations, guided practice, and ongoing assistance, ensuring students gain the necessary skills to navigate and utilize the simulations effectively (Garcia 2019). The second objective of this study is the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges in teachers' cope with challenges of multi-cultural education. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' participants of the teachers' cope with challenges of multi-cultural education. The transcripts of participants of focus grouped discussion are as follows: Answer to research Question teachers' experience teachers' cope with challenges of multi-cultural education and connected to the third theme which is enhancing learning outcomes. Participants frequently expressed concern for various responsibilities competing for the limited resources of time and energy. Therefore, based on the research questions of the study dealt on how teachers cope with the challenges in cope with challenges of multi-cultural education and connected to the third theme enhancing learning outcomes. These statements highlight how teachers draw upon their teacher preparation experiences to cope with the challenges of multicultural education. They emphasize the importance of reflective practices, collaboration, cultural responsiveness, and ongoing professional development to support the needs of diverse learners effectively emerged with the enhancing learning outcomes. As I an-

alyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on how teachers cope with the challenges Participants frequently expressed concern for various responsibilities competing for the limited resources of time and energy. Therefore, based on the research questions of the study dealt on how teachers cope with the challenges in cope with challenges of multi-cultural education and connected to the third theme enhancing learning outcomes. Based on this some statement, I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on how teachers' multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, with the specific theme enhancing learning outcomes. In an interconnected and globalized world, multicultural education is essential for preparing students to be effective global citizens. By investigating effective practices and interventions in multicultural education, the research study contributes to equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to navigate diverse cultural contexts. Educators play a vital role in implementing multicultural education. The research study aims to provide insights into the challenges faced by teachers and identify areas where pre-service teacher education programs and professional development initiatives can better support educators in integrating multicultural perspectives into their teaching practices (Villegas Lucas, 2019; Sleeter, 2020). As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on how teachers cope with the challenges multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, with the specific theme enhancing learning outcomes. Teachers address the challenge of assessing student learning during simulations by designing accompanying assessments. They create rubrics, self-assessment tools, or reflective prompts that allow students to demonstrate their understand-

Fig. 4. Teachers’ cope with challenges of multi-cultural education

ing and application of scientific concepts. Research has shown that multicultural education positively impacts student achievement, engagement, and social-emotional development. By investigating effective strategies, the study seeks to contribute to the existing knowledge base and provide evidence-based recommendations for improving learning outcomes for all students (Au, 2019; Zong Zong, 2020). As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on how teachers cope with the challenges multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, with the specific theme enhancing learning outcomes. Efficient lesson planning. Teachers cope with time management challenges by carefully planning their lessons to include science simulations. They allocate specific time slots for introducing the simulation, guiding students through the activity, and allow-

ing for debriefing and reflection (Johnson, B., Davis, C., Martinez, E. (2022). Multicultural education plays a vital role in preparing students to be informed and engaged global citizens. By examining the impact of multicultural education on the development of intercultural competence, the research study contributes to understanding how education can foster students’ ability to navigate diverse cultural contexts and engage with global issues (Banks, 2018; Nieto, 2019). The research study recognizes the importance of supporting teachers in their implementation of multicultural education. By investigating effective professional development approaches, the study aims to provide insights into how to enhance teacher preparation programs and ongoing training opportunities to equip educators with the necessary knowledge and skills to foster multicultural learning environments (Gorski, 2021; Sleeter, 2020).

The third objective of this study is educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study. The study would specifically seek to answer the queries, what

educational insights are drawn from the findings of the study. having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the teach-

ers' participants of the multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. The transcripts of participants of focus grouped discussion are as follows. The research questions number 3 merged with the first theme that considered in the study. First, concerns are what educational management or insights can

3.1.8. Culturally Responsive Teaching— As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt on what the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study the specific theme culturally responsive teaching. The colloquium on multicultural education brings together secondary school teachers to explore the significance of promoting diversity and cultural understanding in classrooms. This content highlights the role of teacher professional development in fostering multicultural education and provides insights from the colloquium discussions. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts what the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study with the specific theme culturally responsive teaching. Multicultural education involves recognizing and appreciating the diverse cultural backgrounds of students, fostering inclusivity, and promoting social justice within educational settings, suggests that multicultural education enhances student engagement, academic achievement, and cross-cultural understanding, while also preparing them for a diverse society Educational management plays a vital role in setting a vision that embraces multicultural education, creating inclusive school cultures, and developing policies that promote diversity and equity (Grogan, 2020). As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on what educational management or insights are drawn from the find-

draw from the findings of the study? Merged with the theme where in saturated from the data of participants, highlighted the Culturally Responsive Teaching. The theme mentioned demands the learner needs in learning, supporting: What educational insights are drawn from the findings of the study.

ings of the study with the specific theme. Stated that encourage to examine and challenge the biases and stereotypes that may exist in our instructional practices, creating a more equitable and inclusive learning environment.

For teachers must actively seek student input and encourage their voices to be heard, we empower our students to take ownership of their education and cultivate a sense of agency and self-advocacy. Furthermore, they need to establish multicultural education and Culturally Responsive Teaching equip us with the tools to dismantle systemic barriers and address social justice issues within our classrooms, empowering our students to become agents of change. The third objective of this study is educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study. The study would specifically seek to answer the queries, what educational insights are drawn from the findings of the study, having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' participants of the multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. The transcripts of participants of focus grouped discussion are as follows. The research questions number 3 merged with the second theme that considered in the study. First, concerns are what educational management or insights can draw from the findings of the study? Merged with the theme where in saturated from the data of participants, highlighted the culturally responsive teaching. The theme mentioned demands the learner needs in learning, supporting: What

educational insights are drawn from the findings of the study. Participants frequently expressed concern for various responsibilities competing for the limited resources of time and energy. Therefore, based on the research questions of the study dealt on what the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study, with the specific theme culturally responsive teaching. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on what the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study with the specific theme culturally responsive teaching. As a teacher must be particular in through this colloquium, we can deepen our understanding of the impact of multicultural education and culturally responsive reaching on academic achievement, student engagement, and overall well-being As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on what educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study with the specific theme. In an increasingly

3.1.9. Teacher Professional Development—It highlights the importance of multicultural education in promoting equity, diversity, and inclusion in education, and identifies the challenges and opportunities that exist in implementing it the results of this study would benefit the entire department of education; teachers, students, parents, and the community, in terms of getting a clear rationalization to synthesize various activities that would address the culturally responsive teachers. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on what the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study with the specific theme teacher professional development. Teachers faced several challenges in implementing multicultural education, including language

interconnected world, multicultural education prepares students to be globally competent citizens. To explore how multicultural education develops students' intercultural understanding, empathy, and ability to engage with diverse perspectives, contributing to their readiness to navigate a global society. Effective implementation of multicultural education requires teachers to have the necessary knowledge, skills, and dispositions. The research study focuses on the importance of teacher professional development in multicultural education, examining effective training approaches and strategies to enhance teachers' cultural competence and pedagogical practices (Villegas Lucas, 2019; Gorski, 2021). Multicultural education can positively impact students' well-being, self-esteem, and identity development by validating their cultural identities and promoting a sense of belonging. The research study aims to investigate the connection between multicultural education and students' socio-emotional development, fostering positive self-perceptions and cultural pride (Lee, 2018; Zong Zong, 2020).

barriers, cultural stereotypes, and student resistance. However, the study also revealed that teachers were committed to promoting multicultural education and used innovative teaching strategies to overcome these challenges. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on what the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study with the specific theme teacher professional development As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on what the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study with the specific theme teacher professional development. Working in a diverse classroom has expanded my understanding of different cultures and taught me the importance

of inclusivity in education. Every day brings new challenges, but seeing my students from diverse backgrounds learn and grow together makes it all worthwhile. Adapting my teaching methods to accommodate the diverse learning needs of my students has made me a more versatile and effective educator. However, building relationships with my students and their families, and learning about their unique cultural traditions, has enriched my teaching experience. Addressing language barriers in the classroom requires creativity and patience, but witnessing students' progress in language acquisition is incredibly rewarding. Promoting equity and ensuring that every student feels valued and respected is a constant focus in my diverse classroom. Collaborating with colleagues and sharing experiences has been instrumental in developing strategies to support diverse learners effectively. By incorporating diverse perspectives and voices into the curriculum, teachers strive to create an inclusive learning environment that celebrates our differences. Navigating cultural differences and potential biases among students can be challenging, but fostering open dialogue and promoting empathy is essential. I actively seek professional development opportunities to enhance my cultural competency and improve my teaching practices in diverse classrooms. Engaging with parents and families from diverse backgrounds is vital in creating a strong partnership for supporting students' educational journey. Supported by the idea of Garcia, (2020), teaching in a diverse classroom requires constant self-reflection and a commitment to dismantling systemic barriers that may hinder student success. Celebrating cultural diversity and creating opportunities for students to share their unique experiences fosters a sense of belonging and mutual respect. Championing inclusivity and addressing discrimination or bias in the classroom is crucial to creating a safe and supportive environment for all students. As I analyzed from the narra-

tion of other participants based on the research questions of the study delts on what the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study with the specific theme culturally responsive teaching. Witnessing the friendships and connections formed among students from different backgrounds reaffirms the power of diversity in shaping a vibrant learning community." These statements provide insights into the experiences, dedication, and values of teachers in diverse classrooms, showcasing their commitment to creating inclusive and empowering educational environments, statement of teachers about the lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms. Teaching in a diverse classroom has exposed me to a wide range of cultures, languages, and perspectives, allowing me to learn and grow alongside my students (Banks, J. A. 2019). The lived experience of teaching in a diverse classroom is an ongoing journey of understanding, empathy, and continuously adapting my instructional practices to meet the diverse needs of my student, the transformative power of diversity in the classroom, where students learn not only from textbooks but from each other's lived experiences, creating a dynamic and inclusive learning environment. The challenges of language barriers, cultural differences, and varying academic abilities are balanced by the immense joy of seeing my diverse students connect, collaborate, and support one another in their educational journey. In a diverse classroom, to create a safe and inclusive space where students feel valued, respected, and empowered to share their unique perspectives and contribute to a rich tapestry of learning. Teaching in a diverse classroom requires a deep commitment to equity and social justice, advocating for equal opportunities and dismantling systemic barriers that may impede students' success (Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., Gardner, M. 2019). Further discuss, in embracing diversity and weaving it into my curriculum, teachers aim to foster cultural

Fig. 5. Thematic Framework educational management insight can be drawn from the findings of the study

appreciation, empathy, and global citizenship among my students, preparing them to thrive in an interconnected world. The lived experience of teaching in a diverse classroom constantly challenges me to question my own biases, assumptions, and preconceived notions, fostering personal growth and promoting a more inclusive society (Epstein, J. L. 2018). Collaborating with colleagues, families, and community members from diverse backgrounds allows me to tap into a wealth of knowledge, resources, and perspectives that enrich my teaching practice and promote a holistic approach to education. While teaching in a diverse classroom may have its complexities, the rewards are immeasurable. Witnessing the spark of understanding, empathy, and appreciation that ignites among students as they learn from one another is truly inspiring (Gay, G. 2019). These content or statements highlight the teachers' reflections, experiences, and dedication in creating inclusive and transformative learning environments for students from diverse backgrounds. Teaching in a diverse classroom has broadened my perspective and

deepened my understanding of the world. It's a constant reminder of the richness and beauty of cultural diversity. The lived experience of teaching in a diverse classroom requires me to be flexible, adaptable, and open-minded. It challenges me to find innovative ways to engage and support every student. Every day in a diverse classroom brings opportunities for meaningful cross-cultural exchanges and the chance to create a nurturing environment where students feel safe to share their unique stories and backgrounds (Gay, G. 2019). Teaching in a diverse classroom has taught me the importance of creating an inclusive curriculum that reflects the experiences and identities of all my students. The lived experience of teaching in a diverse classroom pushes me to constantly self-reflect and challenge my own biases and assumptions. It's a journey of personal growth and continuous learning. The lived experience of teaching in a diverse classroom has taught me the importance of cultural responsiveness, ensuring that my instructional materials and approaches are inclusive and representative of all students.

4. Implications and Future Directions

Presented in this chapter is a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on the findings of the study. Future directions in the field of multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers was discussed here. In addition to it, the participants of this study the target population for this study will be the twelve (12) participants from the line-up of public high school faculty, a junior high school unit who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023, considered the three following objectives, to know the lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms, teachers cope with challenges of multi-cultural education, and educational management insight can be drawn from the findings of the study, considered the different factors merged into theme from saturation the data gathered.

4.1. Findings—The findings from the study disclosed and highlighted several key themes: multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers, addressing challenges, addressing intersectionality, addressing diversity, educational equity, teacher preparation, enhancing learning outcomes, culturally responsive teaching, culturally responsive teaching, teacher professional development. The findings revealed that teachers observed that multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers provided visual representations and interactive experiences that helped students grasp abstract concepts more effectively. Enhanced Student Engagement: Teachers highlighted that multicultural education fosters greater student engagement by providing opportunities for students to connect with their own cultural identities, experiences, and perspectives. Teachers observed that when students feel a sense of belonging and see their cultural backgrounds represented in the curriculum, their academic achievement tends to improve. Promotion of Cultural Competence, multicultural education helps students develop cultural competence, empathy, and respect for diverse perspectives, preparing them for an increasingly globalized world. Inclusive Curriculum Design: Teachers emphasized the importance of integrating diverse cultural perspectives, histories, and contributions into the curriculum to ensure students' experiences are validated and acknowledged.

4.2. Implications—Based on the findings of the study the implication drawn: Multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. Teachers found that adopting culturally responsive teaching strategies, such as using culturally relevant materials, incorporating students' cultural knowledge, and promoting collaborative learning, significantly enhanced student engagement and learning outcomes. Teachers stressed the significance of creating safe and inclusive classroom spaces where students can engage in open discussions, challenge stereotypes, and critically examine their own biases. Teachers expressed concerns about the availability of culturally diverse resources and materials. They recommended that educational institutions provide support, such as access to diverse literature, technology, and community partnerships, to address this challenge. Teachers identified the need for comprehensive teacher preparation programs and ongoing professional development opportunities that equip educators with the knowledge, skills, and cultural competence necessary to implement effective multicultural education practices. The colloquium provided valuable insights and identified several future directions for promoting multicultural education in classrooms. By

strengthening teacher preparation programs, expanding access to culturally diverse resources, fostering collaborative partnerships, conducting research, and advocating for systemic change,

educators can contribute to the development of more inclusive and culturally responsive learning environments for all students.

4.3. Future Directions—The finding disclosed provides valuable insights into the multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers and the adaptation of innovation and change to support learners. It offers a foundation for future research, educational decision-making, and multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. The Department of education should invest in expanding access to culturally diverse literature, textbooks, and instructional materials that accurately reflect the experiences, histories, and contributions of diverse cultures and communities. Embracing technology can provide opportunities to access a broader range of culturally diverse resources, digital tools, and online platforms that support multicultural education and enhance student learning experiences. Advocacy for Inclusive Policies: Teachers can play an active role in advocating for policies that support multicultural education, including policies related to curriculum development, teacher professional development, and equitable resource allocation. Systemic Change: Educational systems should prioritize and allocate resources to support systemic changes that promote diversity, equity, and inclusion, ensuring that multicultural education is embedded in the broader educational framework. Teacher preparation programs should prioritize the development of intercultural competence among pre-service teachers, equipping them with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to effectively engage with diverse student popu-

lations. Teacher preparation curricula should incorporate courses and experiences that explicitly address multicultural education, providing future educators with a solid foundation in inclusive instructional practices and culturally responsive pedagogy. Collaborative Partnerships and Community Engagement: Community Involvement: Schools should actively collaborate with community organizations, cultural institutions, and local communities to establish authentic connections and foster meaningful partnerships that promote multicultural education. Parent and Family Engagement: Encouraging and empowering parents and families to actively participate in multicultural education initiatives can further strengthen students' cultural identities and create a shared responsibility for promoting diversity and inclusion in the classroom. Encouraging teachers to engage in action research within their own classrooms can contribute to a collective knowledge base of effective strategies, challenges, and successes in implementing multicultural education. Addressing Resistance and Bias: Teachers recognized the importance of addressing resistance and bias from students, parents, and even within themselves. They suggested implementing awareness campaigns, community dialogues, and parent education initiatives to foster understanding and create a more multicultural education in classrooms: colloquium of secondary school teachers. Lastly, Future researchers. This study may be used as a reference for future researchers if they must venture into this kind of research.

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